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Power, Surveillance, and Resistance in the ESL Classroom: Empirical Insights from the University of Education, D.G. Khan Campus

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Abstract

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This study uses a Foucauldian approach to examine power relations among BS English students at the University of Education, D.G. Khan Campus. The study looks at how students perceive and experience power and manifest it in their behaviours within the institution. In order to find patterns and statistically significant links in students' perceptions of authority, involvement, autonomy, and institutional control, data were gathered through a structured survey and analysed using SPSS as part of a quantitative research design. The sample is taken from 40 students, and the reliability coefficient of Cronbach's alpha is 0.858. According to the results, eighty-five per cent of respondents agreed that power operates beyond formal authorities, supporting Foucault's claim of diffuse, relational power, and supporting Foucault's claim that power is not just imposed from above but rather is ingrained in daily activities. This work closes the gap between critical theory and quantitative methods in higher education research by practically measuring Foucauldian constructs, which are disciplinary rules, surveillance, and power/knowledge. It is important because it adds theoretical depth to Foucauldian studies in the context of Pakistani universities and gives administrators and teachers useful advice on attendance policies, grading rubrics, and classroom monitoring. It also functions as a productive disciplinary mechanism, offering empirical grounds for rethinking student participation frameworks to create more inclusive, reflective, and participatory learning environments.

Keywords: Foucauldian theory, higher education, power dynamics, students, subjectivity

1. Introduction

A Foucauldian view of power looks at how authority functions covertly through institutional practices, discourse, and knowledge as opposed to using force alone. This study examines how power affects student identities, language demands, and academic norms by drawing on Michel Foucault's theories. It examines how institutional structures affect participation, performance, and self-perception with a focus on University of Education, D.G. Khan Campus BS English students. The analysis emphasises how routine academic procedures in higher education both govern and generate disciplined, obedient students. Michel Foucault claims that power is more than just something that an institution, government, or ruler possesses. Rather, power is a network of relationships that permeates every aspect of society and functions through commonplace behaviours, conversation, and knowledge. Furthermore, Foucault argues that power is both creative and oppressive. This suggests that it does more than just restrict individuals; it also creates knowledge, defines acceptable or typical behaviour, and shapes identities. No previous study has quantitatively measured Foucauldian power constructs among undergraduate English majors in Pakistan's public sector universities.

1.1 Research Questions

The research questions of the study are as follows

1. How do BS English students at the University of Education, D.G. Khan Campus, perceive and experience the frequency of power dynamics in their ESL classrooms?
2. What are the reported levels of disciplinary control in institutions affecting students' resistance?
3. What are the measured levels of students' surveillance, perception of power and knowledge within educational institutions?

1.2 Research Objectives

The research objectives of the study are as follows

1. To explore the frequency of power dynamics in the perception and experience of BS English

students at the University of Education, D.G. Khan Campus

2. To examine the reported levels of disciplinary control in institutions affecting students' resistance
3. To investigate the measured levels of students' surveillance, perception of power and knowledge within educational institutions

1.3 Delimitations

The study is delimited to BS English students at the University of Education, D.G. Khan Campus, focusing specifically on their perceptions and experiences of power dynamics in ESL classrooms through the lens of Foucault's concepts of power-knowledge and surveillance. It employs a quantitative methodology, utilising a questionnaire-based survey and SPSS analysis, without exploring other theoretical frameworks or perspectives on power dynamics.

1.4 Literature Review

The previous research focused on power dynamics in the classroom and looked at how non-native speaking (NNS) students react to professorial and institutional authority. According to the author, the term "rights" emphasises power dynamics and views EAP students as potentially engaged participants rather than submissive subjects. The study ignores offering an empowerment perspective that goes beyond the hierarchical structure of conventional academic practice, pointing to a void in the body of knowledge about how to go beyond an empowered/disempowered dichotomy. While more research is required to explore how these power relations change in various other target circumstances and political climates, this literature generally shows that EAP can assist students in challenging academic expectations while meeting them. (Benesch, 1999).

Furthermore, Wenwen Tian & Remart Padua Dumlao (2020) examine how positioning, power, and resistance impact language learners' identity creation and how it relates to classroom interaction in a six-month language and culture program. From a theoretical standpoint, this

study investigates Foucault's (1972) idea that human interactions socially construct power and knowledge. This study generally shows that power relations are ubiquitous in human interactions and include resistance (Dumlao, 2020). The study has a gap to be explored in identity formation in higher education (such as master's or PhD students), pointing to a void in the body of knowledge for more varied sociocultural contexts. While more study is required to address identity building across various political climates and bilingual or multilingual environments,

Moreover, Prakash Bhattarai (2020) focuses on the social and educational perspectives of discourse, power, and truth and examines their relationship with the basic concepts of Foucauldian philosophy. The central argument of this research is that discourse is not only a linguistic phenomenon but also significantly influences the creation and exercise of power within a society. In this article, the author explores discourse, power, and knowledge within the context of social and educational settings and contends that discourse cannot be separated from the society in which it is used. "Discourse is not merely a tool of domination, rather it is an instrument of power" (Bhattarai, 2020, p. 1428). Overall, this literature demonstrates that discourse, power, and knowledge are interconnected social constructs, while further research is needed to address the specific ways these relations are negotiated in evolving digital or globalised discursive practices. The research needs to explore empirical data collection from specific active classrooms, indicating a gap in the existing literature regarding first-hand accounts of these power dynamics in modern schools.

Similarly, Jennifer M. Gore (1995) is mainly focused on the functioning of power relations in pedagogy and explores its relationship with the historical continuity of some power methods, even though education has changed significantly over the previous century. This study clarifies the persistence of educational authority by looking at eight different tactics: surveillance, normalisation, exclusion, classification,

distribution, individualisation, totalization, and regulation. Additional research is required to explore how these strategies might change or lessen in more modern, technology-driven environments. This literature generally shows that power relations in education are deeply embedded and historically continuous.

Additionally, according to Luisa Martín Rojo (2022), the role of knowledge and discourses accumulated about languages examines their relationship with the production and justification of political rationalities used to govern populations. The study highlights the importance of understanding the political dimensions of linguistics and its impact on social equity through the investigation of how specific power techniques are integrated into broader political strategies. "Power technique associated with this regulation of language, namely (self) surveillance" (Rojo, 2022, p. 6). Overall, this literature demonstrates that power and language are inextricably linked in the governance of modern societies. The research overlooks the specific role of emerging digital platforms in reshaping these power-language relations, indicating a gap in the existing literature regarding modern technological mediation.

Michel Foucault's theories of power, discourse, and surveillance are frequently applied to educational settings; most existing literature relies on qualitative methods like critical discourse analysis to explore the nuanced experiences of students. This study addresses a significant methodological and contextual gap by pivoting to a quantitative framework; specifically, by using SPSS to statistically analyse how power dynamics are perceived by BS English students at the University of Education, D.G. Khan Campus. While previous research often focuses on broad systemic critiques or elite Western institutions, this work localises these abstract concepts, such as panopticism and disciplinary power, within a specific South Asian academic environment, transforming theoretical observations into measurable data. This approach allows for a

rigorous, empirical validation of Foucault's theories that is largely missing from the current localised body of work.

1.5 Ethical Considerations

Ethical guidelines were followed, and the participants gave verbal consent. The data were anonymised by not making the question of name compulsory while filling google form.

2. Research Methodology and Theoretical Framework

Michel Foucault (1926–1984), a French philosopher, was also an intellectual historian, literary critic, and social theorist. This study's theoretical framework is based on Michel Foucault's conception of power as described by Amal Galal (2017) in his work, namely *The Most Controversial but Undoubtedly Influential: Michel Foucault and his Concept of Power*. The dominated and marginalised are the main emphasis of Michel Foucault's bottom-up theory of power, as opposed to the dominant. Michel Foucault was firmly against the idea of absolute truths in disciplines because he thought that doing so would deprive people of their freedom by imposing control and force. In his analysis of the epistemes, Foucault looks at the underlying principles, presumptions, and conceptual frameworks that specify what can be spoken, understood, and deemed true in a given historical era. According to Foucault, "the episteme can be defined retrospectively as the strategic tool that makes it possible to separate out from all possible statements those that will be acceptable within a field of scientificity, I won't say a scientific theory and which can be said to be true or false" (Foucault, 1980). According to Foucault, knowledge and power have an unbreakable connection since knowledge establishes and upholds the realities that govern society. "The concept of power in question is one of the key relationships between discourse and society. That power in relation to discourse, it is important to see what is called control" (Mukhlis, 2020, p. 73).

Foucault's idea of micropower is not limited to the relationship between rulers and the governed but also operates on a personal level through everyday social interactions, as power is

not only exercised through top-down authority but also through regular interactions. Foucault rejects the Repressive Hypothesis, arguing that power is constructive rather than oppressive. Power is productive because it creates reality, object domains, and truth rituals. According to Foucault, power dynamics frequently rank among society's best hidden things, functioning both inside formal institutions and in casual interactions as societies develop, produce, and propagate what is considered to be true within the framework of the regime of truth, "Discourse for ideology is the means by which the ruling class convinces and informs the populace of their authority in order to make it seem real and legitimate." (Orungbeja, 2022, p. 168). According to Foucault, visibility takes the role of force as control in automated, depersonalised authority. The Panopticon creates a sensation of continuous surveillance by enabling a watchman to monitor every prisoner without their knowledge. According to Foucault, people are active participants rather than passive subjects in the dynamic interaction between power and resistance. As Lukes asks, "Is it not the ultimate use of power to secure someone else's obedience by manipulating their ideas and wants to make them want what you want?" (Lukes, 2021).

This study uses a quantitative, survey approach to investigate power relationships among University of Education, D.G. Khan Campus BS English students. A structured questionnaire based on Foucauldian ideas of discipline, surveillance, and power/knowledge is used to gather data. Cronbach's Alpha was used to evaluate the questionnaire's reliability, and the 20-item scale produced a result of 0.858. This shows a high degree of internal consistency, indicating that the items accurately assess the concept of power dynamics in ESL classrooms.

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.858	20

SPSS is used to evaluate the responses in order to find statistical linkages and patterns that represent institutional power hierarchies.

The study sample consisted of forty BS English students from the age group 18-25 years, and the study employed a convenience sampling technique, selecting 40 BS English students who were readily accessible at the University of Education, D.G. Khan Campus, irrespective of their gender. This method allowed the researcher to efficiently collect data from people who were available during the study period because of time restrictions and accessibility. SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences), Version 27, was used to evaluate the gathered data. In order to generate frequency distributions and tables that show the quantity and percentage of replies for each questionnaire item, the study used descriptive statistics to summarise the data. Finding trends in students' views of classroom power dynamics was made easier by this descriptive method. The results are exploratory and context-specific, not generalizable to all BS English students in Pakistan or beyond. The results were then analysed using Foucauldian theories of institutional control and power in educational settings.

3. Analysis and Discussion

In the section of analysis and discussion, the experiences of students are interpreted through a Foucauldian lens using statistical data, providing educational ideas. The first objective of this study, which examines how students experience and interpret power systems inside the university, is addressed in questions 1-3, 8, 11, and 15. The second objective of this study, which focuses on students' resistant behaviour and disciplinary control, is addressed in questions 9, 13, 14, 16-18, and 20. The third objective of this study, which examines surveillance and the relationship between authority and knowledge within the organisation, is demonstrated by questions 4-7, 10, 12, and 19. Likert scale direction is used as 1 = Strongly Agree, 2= Agree, 3= Neutral, 4= Disagree, and 5 = Strongly Disagree. These inquiries show how institutional power is supported by monitoring protocols and knowledge systems.

Table 3.1: Power is not limited to governments or rulers but exists in everyday life

	Frequ	Percen	Valid	Cumula
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		ency	t	Percent	tive Percent
Valid	1	16	40.0	40.0	40.0
	2	18	45.0	45.0	85.0
	3	6	15.0	15.0	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Table 3.1 shows strong support for the Foucauldian idea that power operates beyond formal authorities. A majority of respondents selected category 2= Agree (45%) and Category 1= Strongly Agree (40%), indicating that 85% of participants agree and strongly agree that power is not confined to governments or rulers but is present in everyday life. Only 15% of respondents selected Category 3, reflecting limited disagreement or uncertainty. Overall, the findings suggest that most respondents recognise power as embedded in daily social practices and interactions, which aligns closely with Michel Foucault's perspective that power is diffuse, relational, and exercised through ordinary institutions and routines rather than solely through centralised political control.

Table 3.2: power is not something that people 'possess' but something that operates in a relationship

		Frequen cy	Perce nt	Valid Perce nt	Cumulati ve Percent
Valid	1	9	22.5	22.5	22.5
	2	23	57.5	57.5	80.0
	3	5	12.5	12.5	92.5
	4	3	7.5	7.5	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Table 3.2 shows that people strongly support Foucault's relational view of power. The majority of respondents selected Category 2 (57.5%) and Category 1 (22.5%), meaning that 80% of participants agree that power is not something individuals possess but rather something that operates through relationships and interactions. Only 12.5% of respondents showed some level of disagreement, while 7.5% expressed stronger disagreement. Overall, the results indicate a clear understanding among respondents that power is dynamic and relational, reinforcing Foucault's argument that

power is exercised within social networks rather than owned by specific individuals or groups.

Table 3.3: Power is everywhere because it arises from all social interactions

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	13	32.5	32.5	32.5
	2	20	50.0	50.0	82.5
	3	7	17.5	17.5	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

The results of Table 3.3 indicate a strong endorsement of Foucault’s claim that power is omnipresent in social life. Half of the respondents (50%) selected Category 2, while 32.5% selected Category 1, showing that 82.5% of participants show strong recognition that power arises from all social interactions. Only 17.5% of respondents expressed disagreement, suggesting limited resistance to this idea. Overall, the findings reinforce the Foucauldian perspective that power is not localised in specific institutions but is continuously produced and reproduced through everyday social relations.

Table 3.4: Institutions like schools, hospitals, and prisons are key sites where power operates

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	14	35.0	35.0	35.0
	2	16	40.0	40.0	75.0
	3	6	15.0	15.0	90.0
	4	4	10.0	10.0	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

The findings of Table 3.4 show broad agreement that institutions such as schools, hospitals, and prisons are central locations where power operates. A combined 75% of respondents selected Category 1 (35%) and Category 2 (40%), indicating strong recognition of institutions as key sites of power in line with Foucault’s analysis of disciplinary systems. Meanwhile, 15% of respondents expressed moderate disagreement, and 10% showed stronger disagreement. Overall, the results support the Foucauldian view that institutions function as structured environments through which power is exercised, normalised,

and maintained in everyday social life.

Table 3.5: Power is not only repressive but also productive, shaping knowledge and truth

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	8	20.0	20.0	20.0
	2	19	47.5	47.5	67.5
	3	10	25.0	25.0	92.5
	4	3	7.5	7.5	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Table 3.5 suggests that considerable support for Foucault’s idea that power is both repressive and productive. A majority of respondents (67.5%) selected Category 1 (20%) and Category 2 (47.5%), indicating recognition that power actively shapes knowledge, truth, and social understanding rather than merely restricting individuals. However, 25% of respondents showed some level of disagreement, and 7.5% expressed stronger disagreement. Overall, the findings largely align with the Foucauldian perspective that power plays a productive role in constructing knowledge and defining what is accepted as truth within society.

Table 3.6: Knowledge and power are inseparable; knowledge helps sustain power

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	10	25.0	25.0	25.0
	2	15	37.5	37.5	62.5
	3	7	17.5	17.5	80.0
	4	7	17.5	17.5	97.5
	5	1	2.5	2.5	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Table 3.6 indicates a moderate to strong acknowledgement of the close relationship between knowledge and power. A combined 62.5% of respondents selected Category 1 (25%) and Category 2 (37.5%), suggesting that most participants show strong recognition that knowledge plays a crucial role in sustaining power structures, consistent with Foucault’s concept of power/knowledge. At the same time, 35% of respondents expressed varying levels of disagreement, and a small minority (2.5%) showed strong disagreement. Overall, while the

majority support the Foucauldian view that knowledge and power are inseparable, the responses also indicate some diversity in understanding or acceptance of this concept among respondents.

Table 3.7: Disciplines such as medicine, psychology, and law exercise power by defining 'truth'

		Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Valid	1	6	15.0	15.0	15.0
	2	22	55.0	55.0	70.0
	3	5	12.5	12.5	82.5
	4	6	15.0	15.0	97.5
	5	1	2.5	2.5	100.0
Total		40	100.0	100.0	

Table 3.7 shows that people largely support the Foucauldian argument that disciplines such as medicine, psychology, and law exercise power by defining what is accepted as truth. A clear majority of respondents (70%) selected Category 1 (15%) and Category 2 (55%), indicating agreement with the idea that professional knowledge systems play a central role in shaping truth and authority. Meanwhile, 30% of respondents expressed varying degrees of disagreement, including a small proportion (2.5%) showing strong disagreement. Overall, the findings align with Foucault’s view that disciplinary knowledge is a powerful mechanism through which social norms and truths are constructed and maintained.

Table 3.8: What society accepts as 'truth' is influenced by those who hold power

		Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Valid	1	9	22.5	22.5	22.5
	2	22	55.0	55.0	77.5
	3	6	15.0	15.0	92.5
	4	3	7.5	7.5	100.0
	Total		40	100.0	100.0

Table 3.8 demonstrates that strong agreement with the view that societal definitions of “truth” are shaped by power relations. A substantial majority of respondents (77.5%) selected Category 1 (22.5%) and Category 2

(55%), indicating recognition that those in positions of power significantly influence what is accepted as truth within society. Only 15% of respondents showed moderate disagreement, while 7.5% expressed stronger disagreement. Overall, the results are consistent with Foucault’s argument that truth is not neutral or objective but is produced within power structures that determine which forms of knowledge are legitimised.

Table 3.9: Surveillance (e.g., CCTV, monitoring in schools/workplaces) is a form of power that produces discipline

		Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Valid	1	7	17.5	17.5	17.5
	2	23	57.5	57.5	75.0
	3	9	22.5	22.5	97.5
	4	1	2.5	2.5	100.0
	Total		40	100.0	100.0

Table 3.9 indicates strong support for the idea that surveillance functions as a mechanism of power that produces discipline. Category 1 (17.5%) and Category 2 (57.5%) suggest that most participants recognise surveillance practices such as CCTV and monitoring in institutions as effective tools for regulating behaviour. Meanwhile, 22.5% of respondents expressed moderate disagreement, and only 2.5% showed strong disagreement. Overall, the findings align closely with Foucault’s concept of disciplinary power, particularly the idea that surveillance encourages individuals to internalise control and regulate their own actions.

Table 3.10: Foucault’s concept of Power/knowledge helps explain how academic systems control students

		Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Valid	1	4	10.0	10.0	10.0
	2	24	60.0	60.0	70.0
	3	10	25.0	25.0	95.0
	4	2	5.0	5.0	100.0
	Total		40	100.0	100.0

Table 3.10 suggests that there is substantial support for the idea that Foucault’s concept of power/knowledge explains how academic systems control students. A majority of respondents (60%) selected Category 2 (agree), and (10%) selected Category 1, making a total of 70 % of support. 25% students chose Category 3 (neutral), indicating some acknowledgement of the concept’s relevance. Meanwhile, 5% disagreed. Overall, the findings indicate that most participants do not fully perceive academic systems as exercising control through power/knowledge, though a smaller portion derecognises its influence in regulating student behaviour.

3.11: Power operates at the micro-level of daily life, not just at the state or government level

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	9	22.5	22.5	22.5
	2	19	47.5	47.5	70.0
	3	7	17.5	17.5	87.5
	4	5	12.5	12.5	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Table 3.11 indicates that respondents generally recognise that power operates at the micro-level of daily life, not only at the state or government level. A clear majority of participants 22.5% selected Category 1 (Strongly agree) and Category 2 (agree), with 17.5% show neutral attitude and 12.5% disagreeing. Meanwhile, 17.5% of respondents showed a neutral attitude, and 12.5% agreed. Overall, the findings suggest that most participants acknowledge the presence of power in everyday interactions, although a small portion remains less convinced of its micro-level operation.

Table 3.12: Teachers, parents, and supervisors exercise forms of power similar to institutions

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	11	27.5	27.5	27.5
	2	17	42.5	42.5	70.0
	3	9	22.5	22.5	92.5
	4	2	5.0	5.0	97.5
	5	1	2.5	2.5	100.0

Total	40	100.0	100.0	
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Table 3.12 indicates that respondents generally recognise that teachers, parents, and supervisors exercise forms of power similar to institutions. A majority of participants (42.5%) selected Category 2 (agree) and Category 1 (strongly agree), with 22.5% remain neutral. Only 5% disagree, and 2.5% strongly disagree. Overall, the findings suggest that most respondents perceive a resemblance between personal authority figures and institutional power, although there is a smaller segment that strongly disagrees with this similarity.

Table 3.13: Everyday rules (such as dress codes, attendance, and punctuality) are examples of disciplinary power

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	11	27.5	27.5	27.5
	2	21	52.5	52.5	80.0
	3	5	12.5	12.5	92.5
	4	1	2.5	2.5	95.0
	5	2	5.0	5.0	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Table 3.13 indicates that respondents generally recognise that everyday rules such as dress codes, attendance, and punctuality serve as examples of disciplinary power. A clear majority of participants (27.5%) selected Category 1 (Strongly agree) and Category 2 (agree), with 7.5% disagreeing and 12.5% selected the neutral category. Meanwhile, 2.5% remain disagree and 5 % strongly disagree. Overall, the findings suggest that most respondents acknowledge the regulatory function of everyday rules, though a smaller portion scarcely perceives them as instruments of disciplinary power, reflecting varied levels of awareness of Foucault’s concept.

Table 3.14: Resistance to authority is also a part of power relations

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	6	15.0	15.0	15.0
	2	17	42.5	42.5	57.5

	3	13	32.5	32.5	90.0
	4	3	7.5	7.5	97.5
	5	1	2.5	2.5	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Table 3.14 highlights that respondents generally recognise that resistance to authority forms part of power relations. 15% selected Category 1 (Strongly agree) and (42.5%) selected Category 2 (agree), with 32% are neutral, and 7.5% disagree. Meanwhile, 2.5% strongly disagreed. Overall, the findings suggest that most respondents acknowledge the dynamics of power and resistance, though a significant portion also perceives active resistance as an integral aspect of power relations.

Table 3.15: Power is dynamic and can shift depending on social interactions

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	7	17.5	17.5	17.5
	2	23	57.5	57.5	75.0
	3	7	17.5	17.5	92.5
	4	1	2.5	2.5	95.0
	5	2	5.0	5.0	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Table 3.15 explains that respondents generally recognise that power is dynamic and can shift depending on social interactions. 17.5% selected Category 1 (Strongly agree) and 57.5% selected Category 2 (agree), with 17.5% are neutral, and 2.5% disagree. Meanwhile, 5% strongly disagreed. Overall, the findings suggest that most respondents perceive power as flexible and situational, although a smaller portion also acknowledges its variability in social contexts, reflecting a significant understanding of Foucault’s concept of dynamic power.

3.16: Where there is power, there is always a possibility of resistance

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	11	27.5	27.5	27.5
	2	21	52.5	52.5	80.0
	3	7	17.5	17.5	97.5
	4	1	2.5	2.5	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Table 3.16 shows that most respondents understand that resistance is always a possibility when there is power. 27.5% selected Category 1 (Strongly agree), and the majority of the participants selected Category 2 (agree), with 17.5% are neutral. Meanwhile, 2.5% disagreed. Overall, the findings suggest that most respondents acknowledge the inherent link between power and resistance, though a smaller portion also affirms its absence, reflecting a significant understanding of Foucault’s concept.

Table 3.17: Resistance is not outside power but exists within it

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	12	30.0	30.0	30.0
	2	23	57.5	57.5	87.5
	3	4	10.0	10.0	97.5
	4	1	2.5	2.5	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Table 3.17 indicates that respondents generally recognise that resistance is not outside power but exists within it. A majority of participants (57.5%) selected Category 2 (agree), with 30% strongly agreeing. Meanwhile, 10% are neutral, and 2.5% agreed. Overall, the findings suggest that most respondents acknowledge that resistance is an inherent part of power relations, though a smaller portion also perceives it as separate, reflecting a nuanced understanding of Foucault’s concept of power and resistance.

Table 3.18: Social movements (e.g., feminism, environmentalism, human rights) can be understood as forms of resistance to power

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	7	17.5	17.5	17.5
	2	22	55.0	55.0	72.5
	3	7	17.5	17.5	90.0
	4	4	10.0	10.0	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Table 3.18 indicates that respondents generally recognise that social movements such

as feminism, environmentalism, and human rights can be understood as forms of resistance to power. The majority of participants (55.5%) chose Category 2 (agree), with 17.5% strongly agreeing and 10% disagreeing, while 17.5% are neutral. Overall, the findings suggest that most respondents acknowledge social movements as forms of resistance, although a smaller portion also actively affirms this perspective, reflecting a moderate awareness of the dynamics between power and collective action.

Table 3.19: Understanding Foucault's concept of power can help students critically analyse social structures

		Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Valid	1	8	20.0	20.0	20.0
	2	22	55.0	55.0	75.0
	3	8	20.0	20.0	95.0
	4	2	5.0	5.0	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Table 3.19 indicates that respondents generally recognise that understanding Foucault's concept of power can help students critically analyse social structures. A majority of participants (55%) selected Category 2 (agree), and Category 1 was selected by (20%) and 5% disagreeing. Meanwhile, 20% are neutral. Overall, the findings suggest that most respondents perceive the relevance of Foucault's concept for critical analysis, although a smaller portion actively acknowledges its potential to enhance students' understanding of social structures.

Table 3.20: Foucault's theory of power is relevant for understanding contemporary issues (e.g., media influence, surveillance, politics)

		Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Valid	1	11	27.5	27.5	27.5
	2	19	47.5	47.5	75.0
	3	9	22.5	22.5	97.5
	4	1	2.5	2.5	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Table 3.20 indicates that respondents generally recognise the relevance of Foucault's

theory of power for understanding contemporary issues, such as media influence, surveillance, and politics. A majority of participants (47.5%) selected Category 2 (agree), and Category 1 (strongly agree) was selected by 27.5%. Meanwhile, 22.5% are neutral, and 2.5% disagreed. Overall, the findings suggest that most respondents perceive Foucault's theory as strongly applicable to contemporary issues, although a smaller portion does not acknowledge its importance in analysing modern power dynamics.

The results of this research mostly align with Michel Foucault's theoretical stance on knowledge, power, and social control. The findings show that most respondents understand that power is not held by particular people but rather functions through institutional frameworks and regular social interactions. Participants also understand that systems like surveillance encourage people to control their own behaviour, and that power impacts information, truth, and social standards. However, many respondents acknowledge the existence of power in everyday life and perceive it as situational, adaptable, and intimately linked to resistance; some even see social movements as manifestations of resistance within power dynamics. Variations in responses, however, point to varying degrees of awareness and understanding of these concepts. A moderate but significant knowledge of Foucauldian ideas is demonstrated by the fact that while some participants accept academic systems and modern societal structures as mechanisms through which power and knowledge operate, others only partially admit their significance.

4. Conclusion

This study concludes that BS English students at the University of Education, D.G. Khan Campus experience power through institutional rules, classroom authority, academic interactions, evaluation systems, and internalised expectations that shape their learning, behaviour, confidence, and identity

development. The study is based on Michel Foucault's theoretical framework and is supported by quantitative survey data. Student behaviour is influenced by disciplinary mechanisms like attendance policies, grading procedures, classroom rules, and regular academic discourse, but these processes also give rise to forms of resistance. Additionally, the institution's surveillance procedures and knowledge exchange reinforce current power dynamics, demonstrating how knowledge and power combine to create self-regulating students who adhere to prevailing academic standards. According to a Foucauldian viewpoint, power is not only hierarchical or oppressive but also constructive, constantly ingrained in routine institutional procedures that influence students' behaviour and educational experiences.

Future studies might include a mixed-method or qualitative approach, like classroom observations or interviews, to further understand how students actually sense resistance and power. Comparative research across several campuses or departments may also highlight differences in disciplinary procedures. Institutions may also think about introducing reflective pedagogical innovations and interactive teaching techniques that promote critical awareness of power systems, empowering students to confront and negotiate prevailing discourses rather than merely internalising them.

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